

Experience of Ukraine in the Implementation of Information Technologies in Public Administration and Providing Electronic Services

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses Ukraine's experience in implementing information technologies in public administration and providing electronic services. The existing modules of e-governance used in Ukraine, in particular, "government to government", "government to citizens", and "government to business", are considered. It is proposed to use the following modules: "government to employees", "government to non-profit organizations" and "government to international organizations" in the public administration in Ukraine.

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Досвід України у впровадженні інформаційних технологій в державному управлінні та наданні електронних послуг

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АНОТАЦІЯ

У статті розглядається досвід України щодо впровадження інформаційних технологій у державне управління та надання електронних послуг. Розглянуто існуючі модулі електронного урядування, що використовуються в Україні, зокрема “уряд – владі”, “уряд – громадянам”, “уряд – бізнесу”. У державному управлінні в Україні пропонується використовувати такі модулі: “уряд – працівникам”, “уряд – неприбутковим організаціям” та “уряд – міжнародним організаціям”.

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Introduction / Вступ

The rapid development of social relations leads to the use of information technologies in all spheres of life, including in public administration. Over the past two decades, the development of e-government and the implementation of information technologies in the field of public administration began rapidly in Ukraine. This trend is explained by global progress in information technology, as well as the efforts of the Ukrainian government to simplify work and facilitate interaction with citizens and internal cooperation between public services (Tymchenko, 2022).

Electronic government (“e-government”) involves the use of information and communication technologies in public administration institutions to improve their functioning and provide electronic administrative services to all categories of citizens and private structures, as well as informing about their work which simplifies communication between citizens and business structures with official institutions.

In a narrow sense, the concept of e-government is reduced only to the usual duplication in electronic form of the current activities of a public institution. In a broad sense, e-government is considered an approach aimed at improving the efficiency of the state in general. The e-government system provides that any individual or legal entity can make requests to public institutions through the Internet to obtain the necessary information and receive certain administrative services.

Today, two main electronic government technologies are known. These are e-Government 1.0 and e-Government 2.0.

The e-Government 1.0 technology is a basic technology of e-government based on providing access to the receipt of electronic services to citizens through the web resources of public administration institutions.

The e-Government 2.0 technology aimed at creating an electronic platform on which the government, citizens, and business companies can improve the transparency and efficiency of government work on the principle of “putting the government in the hands of citizens”. This technology is based on using information technologies that allow users to create and distribute their content on the Internet, and to discuss the information messages. The most successful in implementing the e-Government 2.0 technology are Australia, the USA, Great Britain, and New Zealand.

Traditionally, the concept of e-government consists of three modules:

- 1) “government to government”, (G2G);
- 2) “government to citizens” (G2C);
- 3) “government to business”, G2B).

The “government-to-government” module provides for the automation of management processes and the introduction of electronic document flow in public authorities, as well as the introduction of electronic interaction between public authorities, primarily aimed at providing certain electronic services by one public authority to another.

The purpose of introducing the “government to citizens” module is to transform public authorities into services designed to provide the most comfortable conditions for the life and work of citizens and their self-realization.

The tasks of the “government-to-business” module are: simplifying starting and running a business, activating small and medium-sized businesses, optimizing management, and increasing the efficiency of business companies (Fedorchak O., 2011).

Scientists who studied the implementation of information technologies in the activities of public authorities single out the following modules of electronic government:

- 1) “government to citizens” (G2C);
- 2) “citizens to government” (C2G);
- 3) “government to business” (G2B);
- 4) “business to government” (B2G);
- 5) “government to government” (G2G);

- 6) “government to public employees” (G2E);
- 7) “government to international organizations” (G2I);
- 8) “government to nonprofit organizations” (G2N);
- 9) “nonprofit organizations to government” (N2G) (Fang, 2002).

The following research methods were used in the work: methods of systematization, comparative analysis, and generalization. The work is based on information published on the websites of public authorities of Ukraine regarding the implementation of information technology in their activities.

The results of the study show that today electronic government tools are partially used by public authorities in Ukraine. Although more than 100 electronic services have already been created in Ukraine today, and it is planned to transfer 90% of all government services online, reducing the number of “face-to-face” interactions between citizens and businesses with the government, the work of the government in this area needs improvement.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the process of implementing information technologies in the public authorities of Ukraine based on the modules discussed above, to identify problems and risks of their implementation, and to develop proposals for the public authorities to eliminate them.

Results / Результати

1. Services based on the “citizens to government” module

Online Public Services “Diia” can be considered a digital breakthrough for Ukraine. The service was officially launched in 2020. It consists of the web portal “Diia” and the mobile application “Diia”.

The web portal “Diia”. The web portal “Diia” is a modern and innovative register of administrative services that has no analogs in other countries of the world. It is an online service that provides more than 100 services for citizens. The portal provides an opportunity to receive government services, submit petitions, complaints, and appeals from citizens, communicate electronically with authorities, conduct surveys, access information from registers, and use personal accounts, etc. (Tymchenko, 2022).

It is possible to create an electronic cabinet on the portal that performs four functions: giving a citizen access to his personal information in state registers, for example, information about a property, taxes, wages, etc.; providing access to all e-services; feedback; electronic consultations on socially important issues, etc. A citizen can get personal information about their business, real estate, marital status, taxes, pension, vehicles, and land thanks to the electronic cabinet (Belikova, 2022).

Despite the full-scale invasion, the Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine continues to create new services and add documents to the “Diia” portal. Since the beginning of the war, the demand for electronic administrative services has almost doubled. As of today, the number of “Diia” users has crossed the mark of more than 20 million Ukrainians. The new challenges posed by the war did not change plans for the implementation of digitalization. The problems that faced the sphere of public administration in the field of digital transformations in the conditions of martial law became not an obstacle, but an impetus to the development of digitalization in Ukraine. Thus, the war did not lead to a deterioration of relations between the authorities and citizens, but, on the contrary, gave an impetus to more intensive development of new opportunities and technologies.

Along with the positive aspects, there are also problematic aspects of the implementation of public services in “Diia”. Despite the unambiguously correct idea of using digital opportunities and today's challenges, there are still gaps in the legislation and mistakes in the technological field. These include problems with the registration of internally displaced persons and the assignment of payments to them. As of July 2022, more than 620,000 Ukrainians applied for this status and financial assistance through “Diia”, but only 70% of them received this status and financial assistance. Other persons in the conditions of martial law remain without state support. The delay occurred for several reasons: a large number of applications, the involvement of social security workers who did not have time to process the applications of applicants, and “several technical problems”. Currently, we can talk about the technical problems of the operation of the “Diia” system, as well as the insufficient level of digital literacy of public officials, who are involved in the processing of electronic applications.

Another problem is granting or receiving internally displaced person status only in the “Diia” system without being reflected in the relevant registers of the Ministry of Social Policy, etc. (Belikova, 2022).

Mobile application “Diia”. This is a mobile application, the purpose of which is to provide electronic documents and government services to citizens. The first documents that appeared in the application were electronic driver's licenses and a technical passport. The next stage of digitization of documents was the ability to download a passport and pension certificate to a smartphone. As of today, a list of the following digital documents is available in the mobile application: passport of a citizen of Ukraine in the form of an ID card; immigrant certificate; student ID; vehicle registration certificate; biometric foreign passport; taxpayer card; driver's license, etc. Ukraine became the first country in the world in which digital documents have the same legal force as plastic ones. Documents in the mobile application “Diia” can be used in the following cases: confirmation of identity; during trips around Ukraine and abroad; and during receiving postal items or banking services. The war created the need for a new digital document that could prove the identity of the person. Many refugees who evacuated to safe regions of Ukraine did not always have a full package of documents with them. With the beginning of active hostilities, the state archives were disabled. Digital passports or driver's licenses stopped updating and identifying users. Therefore, there was a need for an alternative that would allow for quick identity verification. As an alternative to paper documents, an e-document has appeared in the application “Diia”, which contains passport data and a taxpayer's card (Tymchenko, 2022).

In addition to digital documents, the mobile application offers electronic services. Using the application, citizens can: submit an application for registration of a person as an individual entrepreneur; apply for unemployment status; get a certificate of no criminal record; get an extract about the land plot; receive social assistance upon the birth of a child; restore or exchange a driver's license; sign documents using an electronic digital signature. In connection with military operations on the territory of Ukraine, the list of new services available in the mobile application has expanded. Such services include the purchase of military bonds, which are an effective tool for supporting the economy and the army of Ukraine during the war. Also, the mobile application has the function of sending information about the material losses of citizens, which they suffered as a result of military actions. This function allows citizens to be notified if their property (private houses, manor houses, country houses, garden houses, apartments; and other residential premises) has been destroyed in combat zones and front-line cities as a result of Russia's armed aggression (Tymchenko, 2022).

The system of electronic identification of citizens. The system of electronic identification of citizens unites all electronic identification services such as electronic signature, mobile-ID, bank-ID, and ID-card.

Electronic signature identification (e-ID) is an analog of one's signature, which is required to access any electronic services and sign electronic documents. The project is developing in two directions: a) the creation of a cloud-based electronic signature with secure access to a personal key through a mobile application; and b) biometric identification of the user in the state demographic register (Integrated system electronic identification, 2024).

The “Mobile-ID” identification is a mobile electronic signature technology that ensures the storage of a personal key on a specially protected SIM card. With one click, it allows users to complete electronic identification or sign an electronic document from a smartphone. Identification by “Mobile-ID” has already been implemented by several mobile operators in Ukraine, but it is not yet available to the general public (Integrated system electronic identification, 2024).

The “Bank-ID” identification is a method of electronic authentication of citizens using their data in the bank where they are served. This service allows citizens to confirm a person's identity online, without the need for a personal visit to the bank. At the same time, personal data stored in the bank where it is served are used (full name, passport, address, e-mail, etc.). The “Bank-ID” identification has a lower level of trust than electronic signature identification and the “Mobile-ID” identification, and may not be used for all electronic services (Integrated system electronic identification, 2024).

The “ID-card” identification is possible only for holders of a new plastic passport of a citizen in the form of an ID-card with the security details of access to the personal data chip. Since 2016, Ukraine has started issuing passports to citizens in the form of an ID card. However, more than three million of them do not contain an electronic signature and, in fact, only perform the function of an

ordinary passport. The ID card is assumed to become a full-fledged means of electronic identification and will immediately contain the citizen's electronic signature. In addition, the "ID-14" service has already been implemented in Ukraine, allowing 14-year-old citizens to obtain an individual tax number during the first passport registration (Integrated system electronic identification, 2024).

"E-Malyatko" project. The "E-Malyatko" project allows you to receive up to 10 public services related to the birth of a child with one application. In particular, it is possible to register the birth of a child and its place of residence, issue financial assistance at birth, register a baby in the electronic health care system, and obtain certificates of parents and a child from a large family. This approach will reduce the number of possible visits to authorities and the number of documents required (E-Malyatko, 2024.)

"E-pension" project. To officially retire, today a citizen must provide up to 10 different documents. The project will introduce electronic interaction with state registers instead of demanding documents from the citizens. Such services as appointments and recalculation of pensions, the appointment of allowances, benefits, supplements, and compensations to pensions, renewal of pension payments, and transfer from one type of pension to another have already been transferred online. Citizens can: obtain information about insurance experience, accrued wages, and paid insurance contributions; get information about the amount of pension; form requests for preliminary preparation of documents; file complaints; make an appointment with specialists with the help of the web portal of the Pension Fund (Pension Fund of Ukraine, 2024).

"E-Health" electronic healthcare system. It is a system that helps patients to receive quality medical services. It allows citizens to control how efficiently the public funds allocated for health care are spent and to prevent misuse. "E-Health" has been gradually implemented in Ukraine. Today it covers the primary level of medicine - family doctors, therapists, and pediatricians. It is assumed that patients make declarations with selected doctors, and doctors register these declarations in the system. In the future, the system will make it possible for everyone to quickly get medical information, and for doctors to make a correct diagnosis, taking into account the holistic picture of the patient's health. There will be no more need for paper medical records and printed certificates that get lost and forgotten. Doctors will issue electronic prescriptions that cannot be lost or forged. The system will contain the patient's entire medical history, and it will be accessible to both the patient and their doctors (E-Health, 2024).

"Electronic ticket" (e-ticket). The electronic ticket is an electronic document that certifies the contract of carriage between the passenger and the transport company. This is an electronic form of a regular paper ticket, which provides for the introduction of a system of cashless payment for travel in city passenger transport. The introduction of an electronic ticket significantly simplifies the work of public transport drivers; introduces a real flow of passenger traffic; makes it easier for passengers to pay for fares in public transport, etc. (E-ticket, 2024).

"Electronic map "Network of bus routes". This is an interactive tool based on the analysis of open data, which provides detailed information about interregional and international bus routes in Ukraine. Citizens can find information about almost 4,000 bus routes (from timetables and intermediate stations to the legality of the carriers) on the map. Passengers can easily get information about carriers: who serves, routes, what fleet the carrier owns, and the validity period of the transportation permit, etc. (Network of bus routes, 2024).

"Public cadastral map of Ukraine". Public cadastral map of Ukraine and electronic cabinet of the State Service of Ukraine on geodesy, cartography, and cadaster. On this web resource, citizens can order and receive service electronic services, such as: ordering an extract from the state land cadaster about a land plot and an extract about the normative monetary valuation of land; obtaining information about the owners and users of land plots; review of the public cadastral map of Ukraine (Public cadastral map of Ukraine, 2022). During martial law, citizens do not have access to a public cadastral map.

"Online House of Justice". The "online House of Justice" is an automated system that allows citizens to receive the necessary services electronically. On the website citizens can: 1) obtain duplicate documents on state registration of Civil Status acts, namely birth, marriage, divorce, death, and name change certificates, as well as relevant extracts from the State Register of Civil Status acts of citizens; 2) obtain information from the State registers of property rights to immovable property; 3) carry out state registration of a public organization with the status of a legal entity, a

limited liability company, an individual entrepreneur; 4) make changes to the information about the individual entrepreneur, etc. (Online House of Justice, 2024).

“Unified State Register of Court Decisions”. This is an automated system for collecting, storing, protecting, accounting, searching, and providing electronic copies of court decisions. Court decisions of all courts of Ukraine are entered into the register. The system contains verdicts, decisions, resolutions, orders, decrees, and resolutions of the court, adopted (decided) by courts in criminal, civil, and economic cases, in cases of administrative jurisdiction, in cases of administrative offenses, except court decisions that contain information that is a state secret. Court decisions entered in the register are open for free round-the-clock access. All text, graphics, or other (audio and video) information presented on the official web portal of the judiciary of Ukraine (except for the texts of official documents) is protected by copyright (Unified State Register of Court Decisions, 2024).

2. Services based on the “government to business” module

System of Public Procurement “ProZorro”. The system is an open resource that offers access to all information from a central database on electronic tenders that have been announced since July 2016. Any person can freely copy, publish, distribute, and use public information in the form of open data with a mandatory reference to the source of obtaining such information (System of Public Procurement “ProZorro”, 2024).

“Taxpayer’s electronic cabinet”. This is a portal where taxpayers can fulfill their tax obligations online. The cabinet has two parts: 1) public part, in which users have access to public registers; and can find information about the deadlines for paying taxes, fees, mandatory payments, and reporting; view and print tax reporting forms, fill out a declaration of assets and income, etc.; 2) private part - where citizens, legal entities and officials can use the personalized tax calendar; submit reports in the electronic form to the tax and statistics authorities, pension fund; submit applications and requests for information; receive information about the state of settlements with the budget, etc. (Taxpayer’s electronic cabinet, 2024).

Diia.City. This is a unique legal and tax space for IT companies in Ukraine. Residents of the “Diia.City” will receive special legal status, special taxation, and liberalized labor relations prescribed in several special draft laws. The main legislative act regulating the activities of the “Diia.City” is the Law of Ukraine “On stimulating the development of the digital economy in Ukraine”. This project has combined comfortable tax conditions with effective tools that help IT companies build a transparent business structure, attract foreign investments more easily, and use additional mechanisms to protect intangible assets (Diia.City, 2024).

3. Services based on the “government to government” module

Trembita” information system. The “Trembita” information system is a system of electronic interaction of state electronic information resources. The main reason for implementing the “Trembita” information system was that there are about 350 state registers in Ukraine, which are not related to each other. According to experts’ conclusions, some state databases duplicate up to 80% of the information, they are designed according to different standards and have errors. To combine them into a single network, it is necessary to develop uniform standards. Specialists have already developed a system of electronic interaction of state resources “Trembita”. Thanks to it, the first automatic data exchange was set up in May 2019. The “Trembita” information system is one of the key elements of the infrastructure for the provision of electronic services, which provides convenient, unified access to the data of state registers. Obtaining access to the data of state registers by various institutions increases the quality of providing electronic services to citizens and businesses. The participants of the “Trembita” information system are state authorities and local self-government bodies, which can use it according to the requirements of the law. Currently, it is planned to connect to the “Trembita” information system state registers of property rights, natural taxpayers, legal and natural persons, acts of civil status of citizens, mandatory state social insurance, state land cadaster, and others (System of electronic interaction of state electronic information resources “Trembita”, 2024).

“Vulyk” information system. The “Vulyk” information system automates the work of Administrative Service Centers and makes it possible to improve the quality of service to citizens. The “Vulyk” information system should speed up the work of the administrators of the Administrative Service Centers thanks to the transition to electronic document flow and simplified access to the data

of state registers in real-time. There are more than 1000 Administrative Service Centers in Ukraine. Almost 80% of them do not have software to automate their work. The “Vulyk” information system, in which the local Administrative Service Centers will work, will by default be connected to the “Trembita” information system. Accordingly, in the future, the Administrative Service Centers of even a small and remote community will have access to the registers of central executive authorities. This means that citizens will be able to receive services in the centers “in one visit”. Relatively speaking, citizens will have to wait 15 minutes, not a week, two, or a month. In particular, the Administrative Service Centers with the help of the “Vulyk” information system can send the applicant's paper documents to the state authorities providing the service in electronic form. In the future, the Administrative Service Centers will be able to directly receive the information necessary for providing the service from state electronic registers without the need to send and receive documents in paper form thanks to the connection of the “Vulyk” information system to the “Trembita” information system (U-LEAD with Europe, 2021).

It is not a complete list of the use of information technologies in public administration and service provision in this document. In addition to digital services aimed at the interaction of the state and citizens or businesses, the government of Ukraine carries out large-scale work on digital transformation work that improves the work of authorities in Ukraine. Despite the war, the government of Ukraine plans to introduce new information technologies that will improve the work of public authorities.

Positively assessing the government's efforts to implement e-government, we note that one of the main challenges of implementing information technologies is cyber security due to the possibility of information leakage, personal data, and user accounts. Numerous cases of cyber-attacks on public authorities have sparked a debate about the feasibility of expanding the list of information technologies that should be implemented in public administration during wartime.

With the beginning of active digitalization in Ukraine, the number of cyber-attacks increased 5 times. According to statistics, most attacks were carried out on the power system, the State Treasury Service, the Ukrainian Post Office, Boryspil Airport, the Chornobyl Nuclear Power Plant, as well as the websites of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine, the National Bank of Ukraine, Privat Bank, Savings Bank, portal and application “Diia”. One such vivid example is the Petya virus, which was created in Russia. According to specialists, most cyberattacks on Ukrainian institutions are carried out from the territory of Russia (Stepaniuk. I., 2022).

In turn, the Ukrainian government is implementing new strategies and methods of combating cybercrime. To this end, the Cybersecurity Strategy of Ukraine was introduced in 2021. One of the strategic goals of the Strategy is the creation of a Computer Emergency Response Team, which works in the interest of protecting Ukrainian cyberspace and constantly warns of possible cyberattacks. Non-governmental organizations and citizens are also involved in the fight against the Russian Federation in cyberspace.

Another problem with the implementation of information technologies in the activities of public authorities is the “digital divide”. The concept of the digital divide is usually defined as a social problem related to the different amounts of information between those who have access to information and communication technologies and those who do not. In general, more than 67% of the population of Ukraine uses the Internet. However, 33% of Ukrainians do not have any stable access to the network. This mostly affects rural areas, where coverage is poor, and wired Internet is either impossible or very expensive. So, with the improvement of the quality of the infrastructure, more and more residents can use the Internet and such a problem as the digital divide should gradually be solved [20]. Information technologies make it possible to make public services not only more accessible and faster, but also personalized and targeted, taking into account the needs of citizens and businesses.

Conclusions / Висновки

Summarizing the research results, it can be concluded that such e-government modules as “government to government”, “government to citizens”, and “government to business” function satisfactorily in Ukraine. The government needs to resolve some technical and legal issues related to improving their work. This primarily concerns the implementation of several measures related to the security and protection of citizens' data, as well as reducing the digital divide.

However, as for other e-government modules, such as “government to public employees”, “government to international organizations”, and “government to nonprofit organizations”, their implementation in Ukraine has not gained significant popularity. In this regard, the government is suggested to popularize and implement the mentioned modules. In particular, it is proposed to introduce the “electronic election system”, and the “electronic population census” as well as the introduction of “digital diplomacy” in Ukraine.

The “electronic election system” is a part of the electronic democracy and partially the “government to nonprofit organizations” module in terms of the interaction of the government with political parties and public organizations. In Ukraine, the process of implementation of an “electronic election system” should be gradual. It is necessary to start from the local level since innovations are easier to start in smaller cities, where democratic processes are less formalized compared to large cities. The “electronic election system” will provide accessible voting of citizens outside the country and automated counting of votes.

The “electronic population census” is a partial component of the “government to public employees” module which is widely used in different countries of the world. To forecast the socio-economic development of Ukraine, in particular, to regulate migration processes or plan the country's budget, the government needs to have true information about the number of its citizens. The implementation of the “electronic population census” will significantly reduce the budget expenditures and will speed up the work of civil servants.

“Digital diplomacy” is a partial component of the “government to international organizations” module the use of which is especially relevant during the war in Ukraine. Today, diplomats and heads of state meet face-to-face with their allies and enemies, covering great distances between countries, making diplomatic visits, and signing treaties face-to-face. At the same time, online communication and video conferencing can complement social interaction. In addition, “digital diplomacy” will make it possible to inform and receive requests from international organizations through social networks, forming an image, and spreading diplomatic news and information, thereby developing diplomacy and international relations between states.

Thus, by introducing the “government to public employees”, “government to nonprofit organizations”, and “government to international organizations” modules, the government will get several benefits. Including increasing the speed, reliability, and cost-effectiveness of processing and exchanging information in the public sector; flexibility and prompt response to requests from the environment, provision of “feedback”; reduction of time and financial costs for management activities; increasing the level of transparency of government work and reducing corruption in the state.

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